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Abstract. During this study, the meaning of such commonly used terms as integration in the modern world, the place of political and economic integration in the modern world, and the importance and relevance of regional integration were studied. Topics such as globalism, commodity diversification, and the relocation of production forces to other places to increase the profitability of production have become the current state of world political and economic integration in the 21st century..

Keywords: politics, economics, social factors, integration, dialectic, objective, subjective, industrial countries, means of communication, concept, globalization.

INTEGRATSION SIYOSATNING ASOSIY KO‘RSATKICHLARI

Annotatsiya. Ushbu tadqiqot davomida zamonoviy dunyoda integratsiya kabi kop qollanilyotgan terminlarning manosi, hozirgi zamondagi siyosiy va iqtisodiy integratsiyaning orni haqidagi tadqiqotlar olib borilgan. Shuningdek mintaqaviy integratsiyaning ahmiyati va dolzarblik masalalarida organilgan. Globalizm, tovar ayri boshlash, ishlab chiqarishning rentabelligini oshirish uchun ishlab chiqarish quvvatlarin boshqa joylarga kochirish kabi mavzular XXI asirning dunyo siyosiy va iqtisodiy integratsiyasining amaldagi holatiga aylandi.

Kalit so'zlar: siyosiyat, iqtisodiy, ijtimoiy faktorlar, Integratsiya, dialektik, obyektiv, subyektiv, industrial mamlakatlar, kommunikatsiya vositalari, konsepsiya, globallashuv.

ОСНОВНЫЕ ПОКАЗАТЕЛИ ИНТЕГРАЦИОННОЙ ПОЛИТИКИ

Аннотация. В данном исследовании рассматривается значение такого термина, как «интеграция», который широко используется в современном мире, а также роль политической и экономической интеграции в современном мире. Особое внимание уделено важности и актуальности региональной интеграции. Такие темы, как глобализм, диверсификация сырьевых товаров и перенос производства в другие

места для повышения рентабельности производства, стали актуальным состоянием мировой политической и экономической интеграции XXI века.

Ключевые слова: политика, экономика, социальные факторы, интеграция, диалектика, объективное, субъективное, индустриальные страны, средства коммуникации, концепция, глобализация.

Introduction

One of the important features of modern development is the interdependence of political, economic and social aspects of different countries, determined by the foreign policy activity of developed and developing countries. These aspects are directly explained by the laws of the development of international relations. Integration processes should not be understood simply as a process that regulates the relations of states. It is a dialectical phenomenon, revealing both the objective and subjective aspects of the same phenomenon. Integration is primarily regional in nature and is achieved as a result of harmonizing the interests of two or more states. At the modern stage of world economic development, we can see various forms of integration processes on all continents of our planet. Since the second half of the 20th century, as a result of the rapid development of leading industrial countries, as well as the improvement of international transport and communication, there has been a rapid development of international goods and services. Along with international trade, the international movement of production factors (capital, labor, and technologies) has also developed. That is, along with the finished product, production factors began to move between countries. The profit, reflected in the price of goods, was created not only within the national borders, but also abroad. All this laid the foundation for the emergence of economic integration. Economic integration is the result of economic cooperation between countries. It leads to the convergence of economic mechanisms, and this convergence takes the form of interstate agreements and is regulated by the relevant interstate bodies. International economic integration is the economic, socio-political and cultural unification of countries, which arose on the basis of the development of multilateral mutual stable relations between national economies (states) and the division of labor, and expresses the interconnectedness of production sectors of varying degrees and in various forms. Currently, there is no single concept of views among specialists on integration processes. While one group of economists interprets integration as a way to overcome the problem of "resource scarcity" by forming new flows of goods between the countries of the world (which will put an end to the

production of relatively expensive goods in the countries of the world and allow for the expansion of technological exchange, that is, reduce costs for scientific research and experimental design work (SRTD), another group of scientists puts forward non-economic factors as the initial impetus for integration (for example, strengthening the country's defense capabilities, etc.). A third group of economists believes that integration makes it easier and faster to achieve goals such as sustainable growth of production, socio-economic and political stability. So, summarizing one or another theoretical approach, it should be noted that integration is a process of rapprochement and penetration of national economic complexes through the creation of a qualitatively new economic environment on a territorial scale. Globalization and regional economic integration are mutually exclusive and, according to some scholars, in some respects contradictory concepts. However, both trends, globalization and regionalization, in many respects successfully coexist in different parts of our planet. International economic integration, unlike globalization or economic globalization, is more of a regional integration. At the same time, regional integration is closely related to the concepts of internationalization and globalization. All this is aimed at strengthening economic, political, cultural, military relations between individual countries and societies. As regional economic integration has become increasingly stronger, has taken a firm place in the world economy, and has become a subject playing an important role in world politics, it has achieved the status of international economic integration and has been directly called by this name. Due to the practically global nature of its geographical distribution, regional integration has become a truly international global political phenomenon. Currently, there is no single point of view among scholars on the processes of regional and international economic integration and globalization. However, over the past decades, a lot of scientific research has been carried out on the theoretical and practical study of the concepts of regional economic integration and globalization. In order to reveal the content, essence, significance, and development characteristics of international economic integration and globalization, it is necessary to consider some of the theoretical foundations accumulated in the world community.

Conclusion

In conclusion, it can be said that the integration policy of states is carried out based on economic, social, legal indicators and interests. This can be seen in modern times in such issues as the interdependence of countries' production capacities, active commodity exchange,

recognition of documents of countries on each other's territory, similarity of laws of states, and convenience of movement of people from one state to another.

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